

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

TESSE2b in POLAND

The 7th TESSE2b Workshop/B2B meeting in WARSAW was another opportunity for TESSE2b partners to discuss and share information with external entities, from academic and business contexts.

TESSE2b laboratory | SGGW

The event also included a visit to the SGGW laboratory, installed under TESSE2b project, that has been used to develop the 3 TESSE2b Demosites' Smart Control System models.

The laboratory is equipped with Flat Solar Panels and Vacuo Solar Panels, with the support of a Heat Pump and a water tanks to emulate PCM tanks for Heating, Cooling and Domestic Hot Water. Besides that, it also integrates a Data Acquisition System.

Stay tuned for more updates!
Don't miss the next TESSE2b NEWSLETTER!

DON'T MISS THE FINAL
TESSE2b
Workshop/B2B Meeting:
PORTUGAL | 18 September

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](#)

A video player interface with a 3D cityscape background. A red play button is centered on the screen. A red text box on the left contains the text "Residential Building Energy Storage by Solar and Geothermal Resources" and "Watch our video!". Below the video player are social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and LinkedIn.

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